

Relationship of the Us Dollar to Inflation Indications in Other Countries

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Abstract: As we all see, the price level is increasing year by year. But this situation is observed not only in Uzbekistan, but in many countries of the world. Why the price increase depends on many factors and is a very complicated process? Is there a connection between the rise in consumer prices and the US dollar? This connection should be studied more deeply.

Key words: Federal Reserve System, inflation, banknote, currency, ounce.

INTRODUCTION

The spread of the US dollar around the world will bring huge benefits to the US by increasing the emission of dollars. Because most of the US dollar inflation is contributed by other countries. The most interesting thing is that the US dollar is the private property of the Federal Reserve System, not the country. The FRS organization was founded in 1913 as a cartel of 12 private banks. This system has the absolute right to issue dollars, remove them from circulation, and set the interest rate. The FRS organization independently controls the issue of dollars and its interest rate by constantly holding meetings.

Materials.

We use quantitative theory to calculate the inflation rate in the economy, but we cannot apply this theory in many situations. Today, controlling the level of inflation is one of the most important problems in the economy of all countries. Since we use M1 as our definition of money, we have to find the determinants of the supply of currency and checking deposits. In most countries, the supply of currency is under control of the central bank. For example, in the United States the Federal Reserve is responsible for supplying currency.¹

Although the global inflation rate fell to 6.88% in 2023, it reached 8.71% in 2022. According to the data of February 2024, the inflation rate in Congo - 46.8%, Sierra Leone - 47.42%, Zimbabwe - 47.6%, Sudan - 63.3%, Turkey - 67.7%, Venezuela - 75.9%, Lebanon - 123%, Syria -140%, in Argentina - 276%.

Currently, 193 countries are members of the United Nations, but only 64 of them have banknote printers to print their currency. More than two-thirds of Africa's 54 countries print their money abroad, mostly in Europe and North America. For example, Ethiopia, Libya, Angola and 14 other African countries print their money, they are published in Great Britain. The People's Republic of China prints the currency of Nepal, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Malaysia, Brazil and other countries.

¹Matthias Doepke, Andreas Lehnert, Andrew W. Sellgren. (September 1 1999). MACROECONOMICS. University of Chicago.

Research and methods.

If the US dollar was adopted as the currency used in international trade between 43 of the 44 countries at the Bretton Woods Conference in 1944, excluding the former Soviet Union, the purchasing power of 1 dollar in 1944 was equal to 17.63 dollars in 2024, in dollars from 1944 to 2024, an average inflation rate of 3.65% was recorded every year, the total inflation rate for 80 years is 1663.22%.

In 1971, the U.S. government completely delinked the dollar from gold, meaning the U.S. government did not back its currency with gold. In August 1971, US President Richard Nixon announced that he would "temporarily" suspend the conversion of dollars into gold. At that time, the budget reserves of many countries were in US dollars. Countries that know the inflation of the dollar demand that the US exchange their money for gold, but the US government refuses to do so. Even though countries with monetary reserves in dollars tried to prevent hyperinflation, in the 1970s inflation rate was very high in these countries. The United States ended the Bretton Woods system by "temporarily" suspending the conversion of the US dollar into gold and making the dollar a fiat (paper) currency. As a result, the Bretton Woods system of regulating the monetary system, which was the basis for international trade in the world at that time, was terminated. At this time, there was a sharp increase in the real (inflation-adjusted) price level for an ounce of gold, but this indicator remained normal until 1970. The real price of one ounce of gold as of September 1970 is \$289.41, as of August 1972 - \$495.28, as of May 1973 - \$725.00, as of April 1974 - it was noted that it was equal to \$1,112.76. The only reason for all this was the rise of the inflation rate in the United States at that time, this event went down in American history as the great inflation of the 1970s. In 1972, the inflation rate in the United States was 3.27%. In 1973 it reached 6.18%, and in 1974 it increased to 4.88% and 11.05% inflation rate was recorded. Between 1967 and 1976, we will consider the 9-year consumer price index in the USA compared to 1967. In 1976, the consumer price index was recorded as 170.1,05%, that is, the consumer price index rose to a huge level - 70% in 9 years. We have considered the financial situation of the world in 1970.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND ITS DISCUSSION

If we take the consumer price index in the USA as 100.0 in 1940, it was noted that this indicator was 128.5 in 1945, 317.2 in 1973, and 414.3 in 1976. If we take the purchasing power of the dollar in consumption as 100.0 in 1940, it was noted that the purchasing power of the dollar was 77.8 in 1945, 31.6 in 1973, and 24.1 in 1976.²

According to the 2023 data of the US Treasury Department, the total national debt of the US federal government was about 31.46 trillion dollars. Who does the US borrow from? As of September 2022, the total public debt of the US federal government is distributed as follows: Civil Service Pension and Disability Fund - \$1.0 trillion (3.3%), DoD Military Pension Fund - \$1.2 trillion (3.9%), other intergovernmental accounts - 1.6 trillion dollars (5.1%), social security - 2.8 trillion dollars (9.2%), Federal Reserve banks (12 in total) - 6.1 trillion dollars (19.7%), other public investors - 18.2 trillion dollars (58.9%). Today, the Federal Reserve System (FRS) is the single largest holder of US government debt.

According to the data of December 2022, foreign reserves are divided by currency as follows: 58% - in US dollars (\$), 20% - in Euros (€), 6% - in Japanese Yen (¥), 5% - Pounds in sterling (£), 3% - in Chinese Renminbi (¥, CNY), 2% - in Canadian dollars (\$, CAD), 2% - in Australian dollars (\$, AUD) and 4% - in other currencies, that is, the world's foreign reserves the majority (58%) is in US dollars. The fact that most of the reserves of the countries of the world are in US dollars depends on the money mass of US dollars circulating around the world, and the money mass directly depends on the inflation rate of that country. there is a great connection between them. The average annual inflation rate of the US dollar between 1944 and 2024 is 3.65%, but this

² Hazlitt, H. (1978). THE INFLATION CRISIS AND HOW TO RESOLVE IT. New York, New Rochelle: Arlington house-publishers.

indicator is only the inflation rate in the US territory. Since the US dollar is a worldwide currency, isn't it wrong to calculate its inflation only in the US ? The Federal Reserve System controls the issuance of the US dollar, unfortunately, the money supply of the US dollar in circulation around the world is not evenly distributed among the countries of the world, and the political views of the countries of the world regarding the US dollar are also not the same, in this situation, the inflation of the US dollar is caused by each should be calculated separately for the state. According to many economists, the US federal government's dollar emission policy and the year-by-year increase in the US national debt can cause an international financial crisis.

CONCLUSION

The relationship between the level of inflation of the countries of the world and the emission of the US dollar is extremely complex and requires extensive scientific research. In the course of the article, I briefly analyzed these relations. With the entry of the US dollar into the international economic arena in 1944, many changes were observed in the inflation levels of countries. In my opinion, when calculating the inflation rate of each country, it is necessary to take into account how much of the country's reserves are in US dollars. The dependence of dollar emission on inflation levels in the short term is very small, but it should not be ignored. The fact that the level of inflation is the main economic problem for almost all countries requires a deep study of the factors affecting the level of inflation.

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